

PATTERNS OF ACCUMULATION OF MODERN CONTINENTAL HALOGEN PRECIPITATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13892756>

Having considered the geochemical cycles of the salt components of continental halogenation at the stages of their mobilization, migration and accumulation within the Aral catchment basin and the drainless regions of the continents of the Earth, we will focus below on the characteristics of the main patterns of modern evaporite sedimentation in continental conditions. Note that it is necessary to combine a number of specific conditions (natural factors) of salt accumulation.

Salt accumulation factors

It is well known that the main factors influencing the intensity of continental salt accumulation are aridity and water content (availability of water-salt inflow from humid zones).

Aridity is the most important condition for the concentration of salts on the Earth's surface and their accumulation. At the same time, the available information on the distribution areas of modern evaporites on the continents of the Earth has shown that continental halogenation occurs not only within the arid regions identified by N.M.Strakhov (1962), but also manifests itself in areas with humid (subnival and semigumid) and even icy (Arctic and Antarctic) climates.

The fact that the accumulation of modern salts is also present outside the regions with arid lithogenesis was known earlier, but no one conducted a general analysis of the features of the occurrence of continental salts in various natural conditions. Such areas can only be those where there is a shortage of the amount of annual precipitation, and, due to the unevenness of their precipitation throughout the year, there are periods during which much more moisture evaporates from the earth's surface than falls on it. This creates favorable conditions for the concentration of salts in water and their deposition during the dry season in such areas of the earth with a humid and icy climate.

The figure shows a diagram of the types of modern lithogenesis according to N.M.Strakhov (1962), supplemented by the author in terms of allocating areas with an annual moisture deficit ranging from 0 to 1600 mm. These areas, although located in areas of humid lithogenesis, are potential accumulators of modern continental evaporites. The largest of these areas is located within the North American continent, and a slightly smaller one is in Eastern America. Vast areas with a shortage of moisture are also found in the south of the Indian Subcontinent, in the middle and upper reaches of the Lena River in the USSR, in South America – along the eastern foothills of the South American Cordillera and in the northeastern part of the Brazilian formation. Among these areas, the regions of the states of Alberta,

Saskatchewan, Decato (in Canada and the USA) differ in the maximum concentrations of salts, and on the African continent – the territory located along the East African rift zone. Salt accumulations within the Lena-Baikal region occupy a slightly smaller area. As can be seen from the same drawing on the distribution boundaries areas with a negative amount of moisture penetrate into all climatic zones of the Earth, up to the Arctic and Antarctic.

Fig. 1. The layout of the sites of modern salt accumulation in the territory with a moisture deficit outside the arid regions (types of lithogenesis according to N.M.Strakhov, 1961; additions by the author)

I - areas of humid lithogenesis; a - catchment area of basins, b - subdomains with moisture deficiency (0-1600 mm), in the final reservoirs of runoff; areas of arid lithogenesis: I - North American, II-African-Asian, II-South American, IV - South African, V - Australian; 3- areas of eafusive-sedimentary lithogenesis; 4 - areas of ice lithogenesis; 5 - volcanoes and volcanic areas; 6 - single eruptions; 7 - mountain ranges; 8 - areas of the greatest salt accumulation within the humid zones (I - Saskatchewan-Dakota – mirabilita 2 - East African - Thrones, 8 - Baikal -Lensky - mirabilita).

It should be said that within the cold climatic zones of the Earth, salt precipitation occurs not so much due to evaporation of salt solutions as due to freezing (cryogenesis). An example of this is the modern accumulations of salts of Yakutia, Transbaikalia, etc. – on permafrost areas.

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